

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 3 |
March 2022 | Monthly Journal by
TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly peer reviewed Journal by **The
World Association of Scientists &
Professionals**

Assessing the Impact of The Non- Oil Export Sector on the Economic Growth of Nigeria

Tunde-Bello Abiola Ibrahim^{1*}, Baidoo Emmanuel Ato Kwamina¹

^{1*}School of Economics and Management, Shanghai Maritime University, China.

¹School of Economics and Management, Shanghai Maritime University, China.

Accepted March 11,2022

Published March 20,2022

Copyright: © The Author(s); Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

*Corresponding Author: Tunde-Bello Abiola Ibrahim

Funding: There has been no financial support for this work

How to cite this article: Tunde-Bello Abiola Ibrahim, Baidoo Emmanuel Ato Kwamina (2022). Assessing The Impact of The Non-Oil Export Sector on The Economic Growth of Nigeria. *North American Academic Research*, 5(3), 100-119. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6370671>

ABSTRACT

Before the oil boom of the 1970's, Nigeria's export trade was largely dominated by non-oil products such as groundnuts, palm kernel, palm oil, cocoa, rubber, cotton, coffee, amongst others. Since the 1980s, the monolithic nature of Nigeria's economy has been continuously threatened by the volatility in crude oil prices on the international market and there has been urgent need for the government to diversify the economy away from oil to non-oil sectors

This thesis conducted an investigation on the impact non-oil exports has on the economic growth of Nigeria. The econometric techniques employed to achieve the research objective includes the Ordinary Least Square technique, Johansen cointegration approach, and Granger causality test was adopted by testing the annual data of GDP, Non-oil exports, Foreign direct investment, Government expenditure, Exchange rate, inflation rate and Trade openness all from 1981 to 2019. The model was observed to be statistically significant, with some of the variables exhibiting the expected results. The study showed that a statistically significant long run and positive relationship between non-oil exports and economic growth in Nigeria exists. The results indicated that a 1 percent increase in non-oil exports increases GDP growth by 0.21 percent at 1 percent significant level. The Granger Causality test also confirms a short-run causal relationship indicating that nonoil export causes an increase in the economic growth of Nigeria. The implication of the results is that non-oil export is effective in diversifying the productive base of Nigerian economy and that export-led-growth hypothesis is valid in Nigeria context.

The study also recommended diversification as a tool for government and policy maker to broadened the revenue base of the country using non-oil sectors to safeguard the nation from further devastating effects of oil shock and enhance a path to everlasting prosperity.

Keywords

Non-oil exports, Economic growth, OLS Model, Nigeria.

1.0 Introduction

Exportation is vital for any economy to increase, improve and enhance revenue and booster in economic growth and development. It is therefore important for economic progress and this is what is characterized in economic literature as export-led growth. As identified by (1) Export is a stimulant necessary for the overall development of an economy which also helps a country attain a favourable balance of trade and balance of payment position for the exporting country provided its exports reasonably exceeds its imports. (2) suggested that when the export base of a country diversifies, it would increase the level of local production of different goods at the same time creating more income and employment for the people as well as further increase economic growth.

Nigeria is the biggest country among the 54 African nations, with arguably the most extensive economy in the continent. However, a look at the Nigerian economy from its export's viewpoint shows that its export is disaggregated into two goods: oil and non-oil exports. These are the primary sources of her foreign exchange earnings (3). According to (4) the non-oil sector of the Nigerian economy can generally be classified as those groups of economic activities which are outside the petroleum and gas industry or not directly associated to them. These include: telecommunication services; financial sector (banking and insurance) services; tourism service (hotels, restaurants, parks, carnivals, movies; wholesale and retail trade; Health services; export trade; agricultural activities; mineral activities; power (conventional and renewable); Manufacturing; environmental services (cleaning, waste collection and recycling); R&D activities; ICT, etc. Each of these activities consists of various businesses which employ and engage a large chunk of the population. For instance, Tourism consists of hotels and restaurants, resorts/recreation parks, movie industry, comedy, carnivals, cultural activities, arts and crafts, etc. When considered from this angle, the general assumption that the non-oil sector refers to agricultural and mineral activities is misplaced and makes the assessment of the sector narrow (4,5). (6) described non-oil exports as the products which are produced within the country in the agricultural, mining, quarrying and industrial sectors that are sent outside the country in order to generate revenue for the growth of the economy excluding oil product.

Before the exploration of crude oil started in 1970's, Nigeria's export trade was majorly dominated by nonoil products particularly agricultural products such as groundnuts, palm kernel, palm oil, cocoa, rubber, cotton, coffee, amongst others. Other non-oil exports of significant value then were tin ore, columbite, hides, skin and cattle. Over 66% of total exports on the average were accounted for by these commodities, and this continued into the early 1970's (7).

However, since the oil boom of the 1970's, the Nigerian economy has become a monocultural one with oil being the major source of income with crude oil earnings accounting for more than 90% of Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings and the implication is that the dynamics of the economy is at the whims and caprices of the price of oil, which for the most part, has been volatile (8). What this means is that, once the global oil market

sneezes, the Nigerian economy catches cold! The major disadvantage of this fragile structure of the Nigerian economy is a situation where the economy has been growing without creating jobs and reducing poverty (9). This could be attributed to the over-reliance on oil earnings from the oil sector and negligence of other non-oil sectors (agriculture, manufacturing, services etc.)

Nigeria has also lost its place in non-oil exports even in areas it once dominated. For example, Nigeria used to be one of the leaders in palm oil supply and presently produces a paltry 1.7% of total world production, which is insufficient for local demand, which is estimated to be around 2.7%. Malaysia, whom Nigeria provided palm oil seedlings to, has surpassed her as one of the major producers and exporters of palm oil. Malaysia and Indonesia currently generate more than 83% of the world's palm oil.

The need to diversify the Nigerian economy from over-dependence on oil to non-oil sectors cannot be stressed enough, especially going by the unstable and fluctuating global oil prices in order to minimize the country's vulnerability to macro-economic risks, such as production fall, fall in demand and price, and also a run out of reserves (10). It is against this background that this study will examine the impact of non-oil exports on the economic growth of Nigeria

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Empirical Literature

Researchers and authors have contended emphatically and additionally adversely on the relationship between non-oil exports and economic growth. The result of these studies varies from one to the other; owing to the difference in methodologies and time frames as well as the variables captured in the models. Various studies conducted show three groups of results mainly positive, negative and insignificant or weak.

Research carried out by (11) studied the contribution of non-oil export to economic growth in Nigeria from the period of 1985-2015. The endogenous growth model was the call idea of theory. Their study found a positive significant relationship between economic growth and non-oil exports using the Auto-regressive distributed lag (ARDL) model.

(12) investigated the impact of non-oil exports on the Nigerian economy adapting the endogenous growth model. They used the OLS technique on annual time series data from 1970 to 2014. The findings revealed that non-oil exports have a significant long-run impact on GDP.

(13) used multi-linear regression to study non-oil export determinants and economic growth in Nigeria from 1988 to 2008. The discovery demonstrates the existence of a positive relationship between GDP and non-oil exports, the consumer price index, and the exchange rate. The study recommended that, since non-oil export was found to have positive effect on economic growth in Nigeria from 1988-2008, it is believed that economic growth could be enriched and become more efficient as the government diversifies its sources of export. As a result, measures to improve and increase non-oil export earnings are thought to be necessary for the country to experience sustainable development.

(14) conducted research on non-oil export growth and economic development in Saudi Arabia (1970-2003). The study employed the use of a three-stage least squares test. The result shows that non-oil exports have positive sign in all the four dependent variables namely: export price, industrial production, population, with two of them highly significant and that at the same time, it is primarily determined by relative price and industrial production. It was thought that population growth would have a negative impact on real per capita income. This was consistent with the fact that real GDP in Saudi Arabia was growing at a slower rate than population growth. Exchange rate had the right sign, but appeared insignificant. The results of the study generally support that export contributes to economic development in Saudi Arabia. The study therefore recommended that, although Saudi Arabia is an oil rich country, which depends largely on exporting oil for the development process of the domestic economy. The role of non-oil export can also enhance investment, production, as well as economic development measure, via real per capita income.

(15) in his study on the relationship between non-oil exports and economic growth in Nigeria using linear correlation coefficient analysis, observed that the performance of non-oil sectors exports was below expectation in aggregate terms and has therefore no significant impact on the GNP of the country.

(16) evaluated the resources obtained from the agricultural and mineral industries of Nigeria's non-oil export sector. They assessed Nigeria's export performance and strategies to determine whether they were effective and productive in diversifying the Nigerian economy away from crude oil, which is currently the country's main source of foreign exchange. Their study revealed a negative impact of non-oil exports on GDP. They contended that the Nigerian economy is still a long way from diversifying away from crude oil exportation, which is why the sector is still regarded as the most vital sector of the Nigerian economy.

(17) examined and analysed non-oil export data from 1970 to 2010 as well as Nigerian economic growth. They used a single equation model as well as a simultaneous equation model (SEM). According to the findings, non-oil exports and agricultural performance have a negative relationship with economic growth. They advocated for greater government involvement in both sectors. According to (18) the growth path determined by GDP growth is reliant on oil exports, as non-oil exports contribute very little. (9) investigated the impact of non-oil exports on Nigerian economic growth using time series data from 1989 to 2012. The call idea of theory was the endogenous growth model. The study used Johansen co-integration analysis, and the results revealed a weak and insignificant impact on Nigeria's economic growth.

(19) used OLS methods involving ECM, over-parameterization, and parsimonious to investigate non-oil and its impact on Nigerian economic growth from 1980 to 2010. According to the study's findings, non-oil exports have a positive impact on economic growth during the time period under consideration. However, the impact was moderate, as a unit increase in non-oil exports increased economic growth by 26% during the period under consideration. The study went on to warn of an impending collapse of the sector unless immediate serious policy measures are being implemented to strengthen the sector. Their findings and predictions speak volumes about the physical reality on the ground in Nigeria, especially given that crude oil currently dominates Nigeria's exports.

(20) analysed the impact of non-oil export on the growth of the Nigerian economy using ordinary least square

(OLS) method. The findings revealed that non-oil export has positive effect on the growth of Nigerian economy during the period under review. Although the performances in terms of output level and revenue generation was below expectation.

In summary, the results of the discussed research found that non-oil export contribution was positive and significant, whereas others found it to be either negative or insignificant.

However, it was discovered that only few discourses could incorporate the proxies of non-oil export but not all in their investigation some selected Agriculture and mineral, some made use of agricultural products only as their proxies, others used Agricultural products export, mineral export and manufactured product export without considering service exports as part of non-oil export in Nigeria. Also based on other studies, there are certain factors that influenced the economic growth of Nigeria. Ignoring these factors could result in an inadequate estimation of non-oil export's impact because of omitted variable bias. According to (21) omitted variable bias can cause the estimated size and magnitude of variable coefficients to be inadequate. To determine this and improve the reliability of the estimation results, the omitted variable must be determined by the dependent variable as well as be correlated to the other independent variables. The need to address this glaring knowledge gap made this study relevant This study will also fill this gap of time by extending the study to cover more recent years (1981-2019) which will serve as an overall extension of all the studies reviewed.

2.2 The Export-Led Growth Hypothesis

The Export-Led growth Hypothesis postulates that export expansion is one of the main determinants of growth. It holds that the overall growth of countries can be generated not only by increasing the amounts of labour and capital within the economy, but also by expanding exports. This hypothesis has been put forward as the rationale for an efficient alternative to import substitution, which is an inward orientation strategy of development. According to its advocates, exports can perform as an “engine of growth” (22). It is proven among countries that the export-led-growth hypothesis is a suitable development strategy for promoting the domestic capacity of an economy through the use of the foreign market. The whole idea behind the model is to inspire developing nations to sustain their development strategies and even make it easy to say the nations whose trade excess of the share of their output appear to grow faster than others. The increase in export volume has an influence on the economy especially with the inclusion or adoption of cutting-edge technology to maximize output. Foreign trade of commodities in kind can help to increase economic growth rates as countries become more and more open to international cooperation and global trade.

2.3 Overview of Nigeria's Non-Oil Sector and Non-Oil Exports

The non-oil sector is comprised of economic activities that are outside the petroleum industry. The main drive of the non-oil sector is the real sector where goods and services are produced through the combined use of raw materials and other factors of production such as labour, land and capital (23). It therefore forms the main

driving force for an economy and it is the engine of economic growth and development. The Nigeria's nonoil sector is structured into four broad constituents which are the agricultural sector, manufacturing sector, solid mineral sector and services sector. The services sector is a collection of several mini sectors such as financial, telecommunication, health, education, tourism and real estate. Today, the non-oil sector continues to be a major driver of the Nigerian economy. The sector grew by 1.69% in real terms in Q4 2020, slower than the 2.26% recorded in the corresponding quarter of 2019, but better than the -2.51% growth rate recorded in the preceding quarter. For the full year of 2020 however, the non-oil sector grew -1.25% compared to 2.06% in 2019 (24)

Figure 1 Oil & Non-oil Growth

Source: National Bureau of Statistics 2020.

Non-oil Exports

Non-oil export products as those commodities excluding crude oil (petroleum products), which are sold in the international market for the purpose of revenue generation. According to (25) on the Nigeria export product guidelines oil export and non-oil export had to be distinguished because of the great different in terms of volume and value of export earning between the two oil export products accounting for over 92% of total volume of export and 86% of total volume of export earnings (26).

As (27) noted that the easiest way to accelerate the nation's economic recovery and development is to broaden the export base of non-oil exports, which will invigorate the economy's oil sector and help place the economy on a sustainable development path According to (26) publication, non-oil export products can be broadly classified into four major groups. These include: The Agricultural commodities and products, solid mineral export products, craft and manufactured export products and Service exports

Figure 2 Summary of Export Trade

Summary of Export Trade

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin, 2021

Figure 3 Export Trade in Goods statistics

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin, 2021

2.4 Trend of The Nigerian Non-Oil Export Trade

A careful look at the chart below reveals that the monetary value of Oil exports volume has been far higher than that of non-oil exports from 1981 to 2019. Surprisingly, the trends remained the same even after serious oil prices shocks and dwindling oil prices implying that the need for oil exporting countries to diversify did not materialize in Nigeria. The non-oil exports have also seen a drastic increase from N199,257.94 in 2007 to N527,839.81 in 2008 and has seen a steady increases from year-to-year recording its highest revenue of N3,788,036.49 million naira in 2019. According to an analysis of data from the National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria's non-oil exports increased from N458.6 billion in January to September 2017 to N1.4 trillion in the same period of 2021. Non-oil exports increased by N942 billion, or 205% over the five-year period. Non-oil exports peaked at N170.6 billion in the first quarter of 2017, but then fell to N161.57 billion in the second quarter and then to N126.47 billion in the third quarter. Non-oil exports totaled N458.64 billion in the first nine months of 2017, accounting for 4.7 percent of total exports during the period under review. Further analysis of the NBS data showed that non-oil exports rose sharply to N577.6 billion in Q1 2018, but then fell to N218.4 billion and N163.3 billion in Q2 and Q3, respectively, bringing total non-oil exports within the reviewed period to N959.3 billion. The N959.3bn non-oil export accounted for 6.9 per cent of the total exports

of N13.8tn recorded within the reviewed period. Non-oil exports totaled N604.4 billion in the first quarter of 2019, before rising to N1.08 trillion in the third quarter after falling to N277.6 billion in the second.

Non-oil exports totaled N1.8tn between January and September 2019, accounting for about 12.4% of total exports during the period under consideration. Non-oil exports totaled N611.2 billion in Q1 2020, N352.9 billion in Q2, and N214.6 billion in Q3, bringing the total to N1.2 trillion for the period under review.

Figure 4 Trend of Oil and Non-oil Export in the Nigerian Economy 1981-2000

Source: Author computation, 2022

Figure 5 Trend of Oil and Non-oil Export in the Nigerian Economy 2001-2019

Source: Author computation, 2022

3. Methodology

The study adopted the use of descriptive statistical assessment for a comparative multivariate analysis of the predicted and demographic variables. This study will employ the ordinary least squares (OLS) method to estimate the multiple regression models. According to (28), the OLS is widely used in regression analysis mainly because it is intuitively appealing and mathematically much simpler than other econometric techniques. This approach, which is ascribed to Carl Gauss, is also favored because of its appealing statistical qualities of linearity, unbiasedness, and efficiency in the class of unbiased estimators, which have made it one of the most powerful and popular estimating methods. The main source of data for variables was the World Bank Data

2021 and CBN statistical Bulletin 2020. Annual secondary data for Economic growth proxied by GDP was used as the dependent variable and regressed against Non-oil Exports (NOE), Foreign Direct investment (FDI), Exchange rate (EXR), Inflation rate (INF), Trade openness (TOP) and Government expenditure (GXP) for the period 1981-2019

The model for assessing the impact of non-oil exports on economic growth in Nigeria is expressed functionally as:

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NOE + \beta_2 FDI + \beta_3 GXP + \beta_4 INF + \beta_5 TOP + \beta_6 EXR + \mu \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

the error term (μ) is a random variable that has well defined Probabilistic properties. It is assumed to capture other exogenous factors that are capable of influencing economic growth.

The log form of the model can hence be written as follows:

$$\text{LogGDP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogNOE} + \beta_2 \text{LogFDI} + \beta_3 \text{LogGXP} + \beta_4 \text{LogINF} + \beta_5 \text{LogTOP} + \beta_6 \text{LogEXR} + \mu \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

The model (Equation 2) was logged so as to break them into a smaller digit and to avoid problem of large numbers (outliers), to explain the result in terms of elasticity and to ensure the variables are measured using the same level of measurement.

4. Empirical Results Presentation and Discussion of Findings

This study will employ the ordinary least squares (OLS) method to estimate the multiple regression models. Followed steps are:

- Descriptive statistics of Variables
- Data transformation or first-stage estimation into natural logarithm forms. ○
Performing stationarity test using the augmented dickey fuller test.
- Performing Cointegration test using the Johansen Cointegration test ○
Estimation of the variables by using ordinary least squares method ○
Performing Granger Causality test.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics of Variable

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of the data used in the study within the period of 1981- 2019. The table also contains the mean, median, maximum and minimum and standard deviations for the total of 39 observations covering the period 1981-2019. The table also displaced key values/outputs like the probability, skewness, Kurtosis, Jarque-Berra, the sum and the Sum sq. Dev

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of Variables for Nigeria (1981-2019)

	GDP	NOE	EXR	FDI	GXP	INF	TOP
Mean	3.10E+13	3.76E+11	96.82789	3.59E+11	1.91E+12	19.14646	29.86004
Median	7.06E+12	2.92E+10	106.7111	1.22E+11	1.29E+11	12.55496	32.28797

Maximum	1.46E+14	3.79E+12	306.9500	1.40E+12	8.12E+12	72.83550	55.02128
Minimum	1.39E+11	2.03E+08	0.635600	1.53E+08	2.47E+09	5.388008	7.522695
Std. Dev.	4.21E+13	7.10E+11	95.99042	4.36E+11	2.63E+12	17.06283	11.53524
Skewness	1.286386	3.176171	0.830697	0.878529	0.930569	1.783591	-0.232691
Kurtosis	3.417148	14.92254	2.848978	2.385020	2.268216	4.997667	2.389818
Jarque-Bera	11.03890	296.5614	4.522434	5.631357	6.498936	27.16262	0.956967
Probability	0.004008	0.000000	0.104224	0.059864	0.038795	0.000001	0.619722
Sum	1.21E+15	1.47E+13	3776.288	1.40E+13	7.47E+13	746.7120	1164.541
Sum Sq. Dev.	6.73E+28	1.91E+25	350138.1	7.24E+24	2.62E+26	11063.33	5056.345
Observations	39	39	39	39	39	39	39

Source: Authors computations using Eviews10, 2022

4.2 Unit Root Test

In determining the stationarity of the variables, we employed the augmented dickey fuller unit root test. We pegged our critical value at 5% for levels and 1st differencing. Our critical number is set at (-3.5) To perform the un, we employed the Schwarz Information Criterion with the critical value set at (-3.5), we expected the t-statistical value to be more than (-3.5) to consider each variable stationary. Therefore, a variable (GDP) is considered non stationary when either the t-statistical value is less than the critical value or both values are below (-3.5).

The summaries of each variables results are shown below.

Table 2 Augmented Dickey Fuller Results

Variables	ADF Stat	5% Critical Value	Order of Integration	Assessment
GDP	-3.501177	-2.943427	I (1)	Stationary
NOE	-7.057327	-2.943427	I (1)	Stationary
GXP	-6.150703	-2.943427	I (1)	Stationary
FDI	-8.026492	-3.536601	I (1)	Stationary

EXR	-5.670445	-2.943427	I (1)	Stationary
INF	-6.889738	-2.945842	I (1)	Stationary
TOP	-7.860968	-2.943427	I (1)	Stationary

Source. Author Computation Using E-views 10, 2022

Summary of Unit Root Test. All variables become in this study become stationary at 1st differencing. We then move on to perform the cointegration test in order to see if there are long-run relationships among the times series variables before proceeding to proper estimations

4.4 Cointegration Test

The cointegration test procedure is carried out in order to establish a long-run relationship between the variables under consideration. According to (28), two variables are said to be cointegrated if they have a longrun or an equilibrium relationship between them. To test for cointegration among the variables, the Johansen cointegration test will be employed for this study.

Performing the Johansen Cointegration Test

In determining the appropriate lags for the model, we conducted the Lag-length selection test and specified our lag length criterion to include 3 lags. We selected the Schwarz Criterion (SC) determine or check the consistency of the model, hence lag three becomes our optimal lag. Afterwards, we perform the Johansen Cointegration Test with GDP as the normalization variable. We allow for linear deterministic trend in data by employing an unrestricted constant with no trend making the constant present in both Cointegration and VAR equations:

Results of The Johansen Cointegration Test.

The table below presents the results of the Johansen Cointegration test. The trace results show four Cointegration equations with the trace statistical values exceeding the 5% critical values with probability values lower than 1%. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis that there is no cointegration between the variables. The maximum Eigen results supports the rejection of the null hypothesis as there are 4 cointegration equations with statistical values exceeds the 5% critical values, having probability values less than 1%

Table 3 Trace and Max-Eigen Results

Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend

Series: GDP NOE TOP INF GXP FDI EXR

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized	Trace	0.05	Critical	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Value	Prob.**
None *	0.921893	253.8360	125.6154	0.0000

At most 1 *	0.847407	159.4979	95.75366	0.0000
At most 2 *	0.628478	89.93857	69.81889	0.0006
At most 3 *	0.536147	53.30310	47.85613	0.0141
At most 4	0.331985	24.88012	29.79707	0.1658
At most 5	0.160841	9.952650	15.49471	0.2844
At most 6	0.089385	3.464508	3.841466	0.0627

Trace test indicates 4 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized	Max-Eigen	0.05	Critical	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Value	Prob.**
None *	0.921893	94.33810	46.23142	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.847407	69.55933	40.07757	0.0000
At most 2 *	0.628478	36.63548	33.87687	0.0228
At most 3 *	0.536147	28.42298	27.58434	0.0390
At most 4	0.331985	14.92747	21.13162	0.2940
At most 5	0.160841	6.488141	14.26460	0.5514
At most 6	0.089385	3.464508	3.841466	0.0627

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 4 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Source: Author computation Using E-views, 2022

Interpretation of The Normalized Cointegration Equation

Table 4 Normalized cointegration coefficients (standard error in parentheses).

GDP	NOE	EXR	FDI	GXP	INF	TOP
1.000000	-0.596919	-0.001729	0.241662	-0.299169	0.001729	-0.005672
	(0.07177)	(0.00113)	(0.05705)	(0.06593)	(0.00113)	(0.00599)

Source: Author Computation Using E-views10, 2022

The results of the normalized cointegration equation shows GDP as the normalized variable, with NOE, GXP, INF, TOP, FDI and EXR as the integrating variables. In explaining the effect of the integrating variables, variables with negative values are explained to have a positive effect on the normalized or dependent variable whilst variables without negative values (positive values) are explained to have a negative effect on the normalized or dependent variable. Hence the results show that in the long run, non-oil exports, exchange rate, government expenditure and trade openness have positive correlation or impact on GDP whilst inflation rate and Foreign direct investment have negative effects on GDP, on average all things being equal.

Conclusion: The null hypothesis of no cointegration is rejected against the alternative of a cointegration relationship in the model. (i.e.) that is, there is long-run equilibrium/relationship between the regressors and the regressand. This also indicates that the original regression is not spurious.

4.5 Presentation and Interpretation of Regression Results

In the table below, the ordinary least square method was used to estimate the correlation between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and the chosen macroeconomic variables. A multiple regression was done to estimate the equation using Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as the dependent variable whereas non-oil export (NOE), Foreign direct investment (FDI), Inflation (INF), Exchange rate (EXR), Government expenditure (GXP), Trade openness (TOP) represents the explanatory variable. The heteroscedasticity-and-autocorrelationconsistent (HAC) estimates of standard error was employed in running the OLS regression. This method ensures the variables are free from autocorrelation and gives a more reliable result when looking at the significant test. HAC estimators have the advantage of not requiring detailed knowledge of the nature of the heteroscedasticity or autocorrelation in the innovations in order to compute consistent estimates of the standard errors.

Table 5 Regression Results

Dependent Variable: LOGGDP				
Method: Least Squares				
Sample: 1981-2019				
Included observations: 39				
HAC standard errors & covariance (Bartlett kernel, Newey-West fixed bandwidth = 4.0000)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LogNOE	0.213157	0.076688	2.779554	0.0090
LogINF	-0.021427	0.033757	-0.634757	0.5301
LogGXP	0.479484	0.100867	4.753612	0.0000
LogFDI	-0.173569	0.061145	-2.838645	0.0078
LogEXR	0.429758	0.071274	6.029620	0.0000
LogTOP	0.099182	0.172124	0.576225	0.5685
C	14.31094	1.109371	12.90005	0.0000
R-squared	0.992899	Mean dependent var		29.35447
Adjusted R-squared	0.991567	S.D. dependent var		2.381813
S.E. of regression	0.218722	Akaike info criterion		-0.040883
Sum squared resid	1.530856	Schwarz criterion		0.257705
Log likelihood	7.797222	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.066248
F-statistic	745.7074	Durbin-Watson stat		1.077825
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000	Wald F-statistic		483.3853
Prob(Wald F-statistic)	0.000000			

The regression result in Table 5.13 shows that Log of GDP has a positive relationship with log of NOE (LogNOE) and this conforms to a priori expectation. The coefficient of LogNOE is **0.213157** which implies that a **1%** increase in non-oil exports will lead to a **0.21%** increase in GDP and it is statistically significant. In addition, the results from the table also indicate that a 1% increase in GXP will lead to a **0.47%** increase in GDP and a 1% increase in EXR will also lead to a **0.42%** increase in GDP. The results gotten from both variables are also statistically significant. However, a percentage increase in trade openness relatively increases GDP by **0.09%** but the result gotten is statistically insignificant whereas a percentage increase in Inflation rate and foreign direct investment will lead to a **0.021%** and **0.17%** decrease in GDP. The value Rsquared is **(0.992899)**. This is the coefficient of determination and reveals that the variability in NOE, GXP, FDI, TOP, INF, EXR accounts for **99.21** per cent of the variability in the GDP. Therefore, the model is a good fit.

These findings are consistent with the results of (29), (12), and (30) who implied that non-oil exports have a positive and significant impact in the long run of Nigeria's economic growth. In line with the findings of (11), this study agrees that the Nigerian government should put in more efforts to diversify the economy and further promote more exports oriented firms after examining and improving their current incentive schemes.

Although the non-oil sector's export revenues are lower than of the oil sector's, it nevertheless has a big impact due to the accessible resources championed to the sector. The basic assumption is that if more resources are allocated to the sector and more policies are put in place to help it flourish, Nigeria's non-oil exports will contribute more to the country's GDP and so boost the country's economic development.

The significant impact of government expenditure to increase economic growth of Nigeria are consistent with results from (31) and (32) They implied that the Keynesian hypothesis holds in Nigeria where government spending is a catalyst for growth. It was also revealed that Government revenue have an impact on the nonoil revenue. This implies that judicious allocation of government spending on the non-oil sectors will produce positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria both in the short run and long run. However, the impact of government expenditure is below average. This is due to widespread of corruption and misappropriation of allocated funds. (33) suggested that proper allocation of government spending would produce a positive impact on the growth of Nigeria's economy on both the long and short run.

The significant impact of Exchange rate has shown varying effects on economic growth while others have shown that exchange rate has a positive but insignificant impact on GDP, other researchers such as (34) implied that it does have a positive and significant impact on GDP. However, the Nigerian government must continue to seek an exchange rate regime in which the rate is decided by supply and demand market factors. Though a flexible exchange rate will result in a depreciation of the naira, it will raise demand for Nigerian exports, which will lead to economic expansion.

The statistical analysis in our model also showed that foreign direct investment has a negative impact on the economic growth of Nigeria. The significant negative impact can be attributed to the weak macroeconomic framework in Nigeria coupled with the poorly managed sectors with the bureaucracy of government agencies and high rate of corruption from government officials. (35) in their paper stated that the Nigerian government still needs to develop incentives to attract FDI that has a greater impact on non-oil exports, particularly FDI in the primary sector and manufacturing sector. This will help to reduce overdependence on the oil industry and increase interest in export diversification by providing incentives and outlets for non-oil export industries to be integrated with manufacturing and industrial sectors. (36) also recommended that both Nigeria's private and public sectors should intensify efforts to attract further foreign direct investment inflows into the non-oil related sectors of the economy.

Trade openness has a positive yet insignificant impact on Nigeria's economic growth. It can be attributed to the fact that crude oil dominated Nigeria's exports of which price and quantity sold is determined on the international market (37). (38) also stated that Nigeria usually experiences too much of importation of goods and services thereby making the country a dumping ground and therefore suggested that importation should be restricted to make the relationship between trade openness and industrialization significant and positive. Inflation rate showed to have a negative but insignificant relationship these findings are also consistent with many literatures which showed the same results

Test of Hypothesis

Decision Rule: If the calculated Prob. Value is less than 0.05 at the 5% confidence level, the alternative hypothesis (H1) of the study is accepted while the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected and vice versa. Thus, the null and the alternative hypotheses of the study as formally formulated are restated below:

H0 Non-oil Export has a positive significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria;

H1: Non-oil Export has a positive significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria;

From the results obtained as shown in Table 5.13 the Probability Value for the estimated regression of the leading explanatory variable was found to be lesser than 0.05% (i.e., it is 0.0090) as such the study reject the null hypothesis and concluded that there is a significant relationship between economic growth and Non-oil Exports during the period of study.

4.6 Granger Causality Test

The granger causality test is statistical tool used to in time series to predict the influence of a variable on another variable, which is usually the influence of independent variable on the dependent variable. It is used to forecast or determine the rate at which an independent variable is able to affect or statistically change an independent variable; thus, how a percentage in an independent variable in an independent variable causes a percentage change in the dependent variable. The Chi-sq from the Granger causality test indicates the short

run causal effects and the decision Criteria is to Reject the Null hypothesis if the probability value of the Chisq is less than or equal to 0.05

Table 6 VAR Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald Test

Dependent variable: LOGGDP

Excluded	Chi -sq	df	Prob.
LNOE	7.954095	3	0.0470
LGXP	6.065850	3	0.1085
LFDI	3.400246	3	0.3339
LEXR	15.80219	3	0.0012
LTOP	4.037206	3	0.2575
LINF	12.21189	3	0.0067
All	60.58366	18	0.0000

Source: Computed by Author Using EViews - views, 2022

Table 5.1 shows that in the short-run non-oil export, exchange rate and inflation rate have a strong Causative influence on GDP growth with their Chi-sq values all lesser than 0.05. We can also see than in the short-run government expenditure, Foreign direct investment and trade openness do not statistically cause or influence GDP with their Chi-sq value greater than 0.05 thus they don't have a casual effect on GDP in the short run.

5. Conclusion

This study examined the current trend and the impact non-oil exports has on economic growth in Nigeria in order to determine the type of connection that exists between them. This was accomplished by analysing data from 1981 to 2019. This is expected to provide a more accurate representation of the economy's fluctuations over time, as well as a true picture of the relationship between non-oil export determinants and economic growth in Nigeria. The study employed the Augmented Dickey Fuller test to avoid unit root problems that are generally related with time series data also the OLS estimation technique and Johansen co-integration approach were used to analyse the presence of long -run relationships while the Granger causality test were performed to check for the presence of short run relationships

The finding from our study showed non-oil exports has a significant positive impact on the economic development of Nigeria. The empirical results from this study found that a 1 percent increase in non-oil exports increases the GDP by 0.28 percent. The findings also indicated a long and short run relationship exist between non-oil exports and the growth of Nigeria's economy.

The results in this study attests that non-oil exports have been effective for Nigeria's economic growth and as such efforts should be made to increase the tempo of economic activities in the non-oil sectors of the economy

Recommendations

Since non-oil export was found to have a positive impact with economic growth in Nigeria over the period of 1981-2019, initiatives to improve and raise the sector's earnings are regarded to be required for the country to achieve long-term development. Furthermore, the study recommends the following line of actions to enhance the impact of non-oil exports on the growth of Nigerian economy.

1. Encouragement of Export Promotion: The Nigerian government should strive to support various export promotion programmes and institutions. This could be attained by encouraging financial institutions, both formal and informal, to make loans available at reduced rates of interest for investors as to increase the level of investment in this country.

2. Diversification of Export Base: There should be a fast and quick transition from monoculture economy to a multicultural one. This is because the oil on which Nigeria relies is susceptible to shocks beyond the country's control. As a result, crude oil earnings should be put to good use in order for Nigeria's economy to become self-sustaining.

3 Efficient Resource Allocation and Use: If Nigeria's non-oil exports are to improve, the government's resources must be appropriately distributed and utilized and curb corruption

4 Political Stability: The political condition of this country has to remain stable as to attract both foreign and local investments in Nigeria. This is because on investor will be willing to invest in an atmosphere of politically instability were policy change rapidly

5 Making legislation that encourages and facilitates local and foreign investment in non-oil sectors such as agriculture, solid minerals, and industry.

References

1. Omojolaibi JA, Mesagan EP, Adeyemi OS. The impact of non-oil exports on domestic investment in Nigeria. 2015;4(3):15–29.
2. World Trade Organization . Annual report 2010. EPPO Bull [Internet]. 2011;41(3):467–76. Available from: www.wto.org
3. Aladejare SA, Saidi A. Determinants of Non-oil Export and Economic Growth in Nigeriaplication of the Bound Test Approach. J Adv Dev Econ. 2018;
4. Onwualu AP. Growth and development of the nigerian non-oil sector: key to sucessful economic diversification. Present 51 AGM/CONFERENCE NACCIMA, Sagamu, Remu, Ogun State. 2012;
5. Dauda TO, Asiribo OE, Akinbode SO, Saka JO, Salahu BF. An assessment of the roles of irrigation farming in the millennium development goals. African J Agric Res. 2009;4(5):445–50.
6. Ulakpa, N. M. Impact Of Non-Oil Export On Nigerian Economy (1986-2010) A Research Project Submitted In Partial Fulfillment Of The Requirements For The Award Of Bachelor Of Science (B.Sc) Degree In Economics Department Of Economics Faculty Of Management And Social Scie. 2013;1–53.
7. Ogunjimi O, Aderinto E, Ogunro T. An Empirical Analysis on the Relationship between Non-Oil Exports and Economic Growth in Nigeria. Int J Acad Res Bus Soc Sci. 2015;5(12):68–78.

8. Enoma, A., Isedu M'. The Impact of Financial Sector Reforms on Non-Oil Export in Nigeria. *J Econ.* 2011;2(2):115–20.
9. Onodugo VA, Marius I, Oluchukwu A. Non-Oil Export and Economic Growth in Nigeria: a Time Series Econometric Model. *Int J Bus Manag Res.* 2013;3(2):115–24.
10. Olorunfemi, F and Raheem UA. Sustainable Tourism Development in Africa: the imperative for Tourists/host communities security. *J Sustain Dev Africa.* 2008;10(3):201–20.
11. Kromtit MJ, Kanadi C, Ndangra DP, Lado S. Contribution of Non Oil Exports to Economic Growth in Nigeria (1985-2015). *Int J Econ Financ.* 2017;9(4):253.
12. Adewale A., Anthony A., Awujola A. The Impact of Non-oil Exports on the Nigerian Economy''. In: International conference on social science and Law (ICSSL), Nigerian Turkish Nile University. Abuja; 2016. p. 1–16.
13. Usman OA. Non-Oil Export Determinant and Economic Growth Nigeria. *Eur J Bus Manag Sci.* 2010;3(3):227–35.
14. Aljarrah MA. Non-oil export growth and economic development in Saudi Arabia: A simultaneous equations approach. *J Gulf Arab Penins Stud.* 2008;34(129):25–44.
15. Asanebi R. An analysis of Nigeria's non-oil export performance (1986-1998). A B.sc project report, Department of Economics. ENUGU; 2007.
16. Adenugba AA, Dipo SO. Non-Oil Exports in the Economic Growth of Nigeria: A Study of Agricultural and Mineral Resources. *J Educ Soc Res.* 2013;3(May):403–18.
17. Raheem I, Busari A. Non-Oil Export and Economic Growth in Nigeria: Does Methodology Matter? *J Asian Dev Stud.* 2013;2(2):21–34.
18. Gatawa NM, Dalhatu A. An Impact Analysis of Export-Led Growth Strategy in Nigeria (1980 – 2015). *International J Adv Stud Econ Public Sect Manag.* 2017;5(2):157–87.
19. Abogan OP, Akinola EB, Baruwa OI. Non-oil export and Economic growth in Nigeria (1980-2011). *J Res Econ Int Financ.* 2014;3(1):1–11.
20. Olurankinse KI, Fatukasi TU. Trade Orientation, Distortions and Growth in Developing Countries. *J Dev Econ.* 2012;39(2):31–57.
21. Wooldridge JM. *Econometric Analysis of Cross Section and Panel Data.*, The MIT Press, editor. Cambridge, Massachusetts London, England: The MIT Press; 2001.
22. Medina-Smith EJ. Is the export-led growth hypothesis valid for developing countries? A case study of Costa Rica. In: *Policy Issues in International Trade and Commodities.* 2001. p. 1–51.
23. Ernest Usoro A, Akintunde Yusuf W, O. N. Okafor B. Nexus between Non-Oil Sectoral Contribution and Economic Growth in Nigeria 1981-2018. *Econ Financ Lett.* 2020;7(1):13–22.
24. National Bureau of Statistics. Nigerian Gross Domestic Product Report Quarter Three [Internet]. National Bureau of Statistics Quarterly Report, 2016. 2020. Available from: <http://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/nanapages/download/329>
25. CBN. EXPORT GUIDELINES. CBN Publ. 1998;5(4).
26. CBN. Annual statement of Account. 2001.
27. Soludo C. Repositioning Nigeria For Regional Economic Power. In: *A Paper Presented by the CBN Governor at the Seminar Organized by Nigeria Export Position Council*". Lagos; 2004.
28. Gujarati DN. Gujarati, D.N. 2004. *Basic Econometrics.* 4th ed. McGraw-Hil T, editor. New York: Gary Burke; 2004.

29. Ekeke S, Uprasen U. An Empirical Analysis of the Impact of Non-oil Exports on the Economic Development of Nigeria. *J Int Trade Commer.* 2020;16(5):39–60.
30. Nwodo OS, Asogwa F. Global Integration, Non-Oil Export and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *Acad J Econ Stud.* 2017;3(1):59–67.
31. Aigbeyisi OS. The relative impacts of capital and recurrent expenditures on Nigeria's economy (1980-2011). *Am J Econ.* 2013;3(5):210-221.
32. Akanbi OA. Government expenditure in Nigeria: Determinants and trends. *Mediterr J Soc Sci.* 2014;5(27):98–107.
33. Olayungbo DO, Olayemi OF. Dynamic relationships among non-oil revenue, government spending and economic growth in an oil producing country: Evidence from Nigeria. *Futur Bus Journal.* 2018;4(2):246-260.
34. Sani AI, Yakubu A, Alehile k. S. EXCHANGE RATE AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA. *Lafia J Econ Manag Sci.* 2019;4(2):22–37.
35. Okechukwu OG, Vita GD, Luo Y. The Impact of FDI on Nigeria's Export Performance: A Sectoral Analysis. *J Econ Stud.* 2018;45(5):1088-1103.
36. Ndugbu MO, Otiwu KC, Uzowuru LN. Foreign Direct Investment and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics.* *South Asian J Soc Stud Econ.* 2021;11(3):29–42.
37. Olufemi SM. Trade Openness and Economic Growth in Nigeria: Further Evidence on the Causality Issue. *South African J Econ Manag.* 2004;7(2):299–315.
38. Adebayo MO, Deborah BA, Nusirat OG, Oshodi AF. Impact of Trade Openness on Industrialization in Nigeria. *Pakistan J Humanit Soc Sci.* 2020;8(1):15–22.

Author*: Tunde-Bello Abiola Ibrahim e-mail

address- tundebellochoco@gmail.com

© 2022 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license

[\(http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/\)](http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

